

THE IMPORTANCE OF MRI DIAGNOSTICS IN THE EARLY PHASE OF AVASCULAR NECROSIS OF THE FEMORAL HEAD

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Relevance: To date, there is no agreement on the etiology of osteonecrosis and risk factors. In the latest International Classification of Diseases (ICTY-10), osteonecrosis is involved in the following classification: idiopathic avascular necrosis of bone associated with isolation and secondary trauma (post-traumatic), medications and other causes. The causes of AN are characterized by such reasons as hurt to hematopoietic cells, mineralization of bone tissue, and this often leads to failure of blood supply. It is clear that the X-ray examination method can only open changes that occur in bone tissue. Presently, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) is used in the diagnosis of avascular necrosis, which allows recording images of changes. MRI is the only diagnostic method that provides high quality not only bone tissue, however also visualization of soft tissue structures of the bone marrow, muscle tissue and other musculoskeletal systems. Moreover, bone has sensibility and specificity in detecting edema and infiltration into tissue.

The target of this study is the capability of MRI and X-ray diagnostics to estimate and clarify the condition of bone marrow, synovium, articular cartilage, fibrous tissue, soft tissue bones and bone circumference in AN.

Materials and methods: Data from 62 patients were taken as material for the study. Among them, 26 men and 36 women, aged 30-66 years, a total of 76 joints were injured. When examining the medical history, only patients with idiopathic avascular necrosis were contained in the study; post-traumatic drug-induced AN were not included. All patients experience general clinical examination, X-ray examination and MRI tomography.

Results: In the original stage (zero) (5). Patients complained of intermittent pain and increased pain during physical activity; the usual location of pain was in the cavity area. At this level, the range of motion in the joint is practically not damaged. There was no evidence of avascular necrosis on radiographs. Radiographs show linear illumination of the bone tissue in the subchondral region parallel to the joints. The femoral head has retained its spherical shape. AN cannot be diagnosed due to the absence of radiological signs. MRI imaging is a phenomenal method for non-invasive assessment of the condition of bone tissue. With a sequence of different pulses on MRI scans, hematopoietic and adipose bone marrow are characterized by different illumination parameters, which allows them to be distinguished. Generally, the bone cuticle consists of 80% fatty tissue, so on MRI scans it appears high intensity on T1-weighted images (T1-VI) and moderate intensity on T2-weighted images (T2-VI). Hematopoietic bone marrow contains 2 times less fat than water and protein. With T2-VI, its intensity varies from moderate to high, and with T1-VI - from low to moderate, depending on the age of the patient. As a consequence, T1-VI is the most informative for assessing the ratio of fat and hematopoietic bone marrow.

Conclusions

1. In the clinical signs of the early level of AN, the localization and nature of pain, its duration, limitation of movements and lameness come first, which requires the attending physician to take a responsible approach to the development of AN, especially in the presence of risk factors.

2. The leading method for diagnosing AN, in particular in the early stages of the disease is MRI which allows one to determine the presence of a pathological process, its bigness and location, tactics and extent of surgical intervention, as well as evaluate its effectiveness.
3. One of the early MRI signs of AN is swelling and necrosis of the bone cuticle.
4. MRI scanning unveils early changes in AN in the contralateral joint in 50% of patients.

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